

Sample 03a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0131
	{Ca}	19.3
	{Fe}	16.0
	{Si}	9.4
	{Si, Ca HiP}	9.2
	{S, Ca}	8.5
	{Al, Ca}	7.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	5.2
	{Ca, Fe}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.9
	{Al, Si}	2.8
	{Al, S, Ca}	1.7
	{Mg, Ca}	1.7
	{Mg, Fe}	1.2
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Mg, Si}	0.9
	{Mg}	0.8
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Na, S}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Al, Si, K}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Na, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Si, K}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	9.9
Pellet	1.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	7.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.7
BOF converter slag	22.2
BOF converter slag slopping	3.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	8.6
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	7.6
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.0
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	5.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.4
Coal and cokes or soil	3.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	4.7
Carbon rich - other	4.3
Cement or BOF converter	1.9
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.7
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	5.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.3
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	19.1
Site - ore / hot metal	1.7
Site - slag	42.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	5.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.4
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.5
Site - carbon-rich other	4.7
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.9
Urban	1.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	5.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 03b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0027
	{Fe}	17.1
	{Ca}	17.1
	{Al, Ca}	9.2
	{Si}	8.8
	{Si, Ca HIP}	8.3
	{S, Ca}	7.7
	{Si, S, Ca}	5.2
	{Ca, Fe}	3.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.1
	{Al, Si}	3.0
	{Al, S, Ca}	1.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.6
	{Mg, Fe}	1.5
	{Mg, Ca}	1.4
	{Al, Si, K}	1.1
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg}	0.8
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.7
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, S}	0.3
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.2
	{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, S, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	11.6
Pellet	2.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	9.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.7
BOF converter slag	19.3
BOF converter slag slopping	3.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	9.1
Desulph slag	1.0
Ca-aluminate slag	9.4
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	5.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.3
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.4
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	1.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.4
Carbon rich - other	1.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.1
Cement	0.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.7
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	6.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.2
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.1
Unassigned other	1.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	29.6
Site - ore / hot metal	1.7
Site - slag	41.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	5.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.3
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.4
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	1.8
Site - carbon-rich other	3.4
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.4
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.1
Urban	1.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	6.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 03c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0032
	{Fe}	18.4
	{Ca}	17.5
	{Si}	9.5
	{Si, Ca HiP}	7.9
	{Al, Ca}	7.7
	{S, Ca}	7.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	4.8
	{Ca, Fe}	4.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.1
	{Al, Si}	3.0
	{Al, S, Ca}	1.8
	{Mg, Fe}	1.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.3
	{Mg, Si}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Si, Fe}	0.8
	{Mg}	0.8
	{Al, Si, K}	0.6
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.4
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, S}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.1
	{Na, S, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	16.4
Pellet	0.9
Ore preparation undifferentiated	9.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	1.3
BOF converter slag	16.8
BOF converter slag slopping	3.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	7.0
Desulph slag	1.1
Ca-aluminate slag	7.9
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.7
Olivine flux	0.8
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	5.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	3.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.2
Carbon rich - other	3.9
Cement or BOF converter	2.0
Cement	0.3
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.3
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	5.7
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.3
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.2
Unassigned other	1.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	26.4
Site - ore / hot metal	1.3
Site - slag	35.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	5.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.3
Site - carbon-rich other	3.2
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	3.9
Urban; rarely site - slag	2.0
Urban	0.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	5.7
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.9

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels